

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE HUMANITARIAN COMPONENT OF THE ACADEMIC SUBJECT "PHYSICAL EDUCATION".

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Annotation: *There have been considered some trends of the humanitarisation of the curriculum promoting the importance of the humanitarian component of the educational subject "Physical training".*

Key words: *humanitarization, general humanitarian basis of education, humanitarian-developing educational environment.*

In higher education the discipline "Physical Education" is presented as an essential component of a holistic development of a personality, of the formation of professional and personal-value orientations, psychophysical formation and training of the student during the educational period. Although there are a number of treatises about the issues of development of physical culture of students in the educational process, the problem of updating the humanitarian aspects of this discipline in the learning process requires further study and development. The analysis of the scientific literature indicates that virtually there are no works, in which a holistic system of implementing the principle of humanitarization of physical education in high school is presented; there are no studies that reveal its informative demonstration and procedure implementation. In theory and practice of higher education the substantial and procedural possibilities of physical training to overcome the shortage of humanitarian culture in the socio-cultural environment of the university are not worked out and are not disclosed, the undeveloped state of the problem can be traced to the conceptual-theoretical, structural-technological and methodological-applied levels. We have developed conceptual-theoretical model of

humanitarian-developing educational environment [2, 4, 5], and now we consider some of the insufficiently investigated components of humanitarization of teaching of the discipline "Physical Culture", which promote the formation of personality core competencies which are included in the structure of the general humanitarian basis of education.

1. The Ethical-axiological component provides elicitation and full using of the ethical and humanistic potential of physical culture. As noted in [10], the axiological component of physical culture consists of relatively stable values of physical training, which are made personally significant to the student. In the implementation of the content of education it is crucial to help students in active immersion into the space of physical culture with its diverse values. This requires training in self-knowledge, self-regulation, self-management, self-organization, self-education and self-perfection. Assimilating and transforming socially necessary social and group values, the students build their own system of values, the elements of which take the form of axiological functions. The ethical-axiological component in the structure of the proposed model not only includes the assimilation of the values of the actual physical culture, but also involves reflection of the struggle of personalities and intellects in the process of teaching, situations of moral choice faced by an individual in the process of physical and sports practice, with emphasis on axiological, ethical and social aspects. From ancient times to the present the history of physical culture and sports has been an endless source of illustrative material of this nature.

2. The History-generalized and correlation-synchronized component aims at enhancing the use of the principle of historicism in teaching with the synchronic relationships and dependencies between the development of all the activities and knowledge of the human society history; provides a multi-faceted use of the extended concept of historicism in teaching. At each stage of human development there were their own levels of development of physical culture as part of the general culture of the person. Extended concept of historicism implies, in

particular, along with a brief historical note about the history of the event, giving a brief socio-cultural panorama of the era, which occurred in the context of a particular event (e.g. the appearance of football), including the historical setting of the period, the level of development of culture and the various areas of knowledge, analyzing the interrelations and interdependence of science, culture (especially physical) and society. It is expedient to make a historical-retrospective analysis of the evolution of the ideas and principles of physical culture, historical digressions, allowing tracing the "times connection".

3. The Philosophical-methodological component is determined by the need to include the issues of formation of methodological culture, including methods of cognitive, professional, communicative and axio-logical activities, in the contents of professional education. It generates ways of thinking and acting, i.e. the procedures of reflexive nature. Modern civilization is characterized by a new type of socio-cultural education, in which main thing is to prepare for the mastery of the methods and content of knowledge and the aim of training is not only getting the result, but first of all mastering the methodology of the activity and its means. Used purposefully this approach becomes gradually the style of socially and professionally oriented thinking of a person, in the structure of which the values of physical education are updated and systematically arranged.

4. The Integrative-applicative component based on our concept of integrative-correlative relations that imply the establishment and use of multilateral relations between both various academic disciplines and between different areas of knowledge and culture. This component aims to provide the formation of a harmonious vision of the world in a variety of relationships and dependencies. The focus of this component is related to dealing with the challenge of building a holistic view of physical culture and its relation to other fields of knowledge: history, philosophy, ecology, etc. Introduction to the content of the training the data of the biomechanics (physics, mathematics), the dynamic anatomy and kinesiology

(biology), sociology of physical culture (Social Sciences) enriches the process of development of the intellectual potential of physical culture significantly.

5. The Interactional-gnostic component of humanitarization of education, providing integration at the level of different ontological ways of cognition of the world, allows by means of the subject "Physical Culture" to make sense of a system of "human - world" at different levels of its functioning, teaching figurative, visual thinking, with the translation from the objective external language into the internal language of figurative conceptual models of reality. For example, Oriental and European techniques of physical perfection are based on different ways of practical knowledge of the world: image-intuitive, artistic - East techniques, and logical-and-analytical, scientific -European techniques, so a deliberate analysis and not a blind perception of the ontological and epistemo-logical aspects underlying them can contribute to the formation of an integrated system of value and meaning systems, to the understanding of the multifaceted nature of the world, its ambiguity.

6. The Antropognostic component implies the introduction of an-thropocentric knowledge and the implementation of technology into the educational material, as, probably, in no sphere of human activity the biosocial nature of a human manifests itself in such an unity as in physical education, in which millennial experience of previous generations is concentrated and stored, ensuring the viability and survival of the human population. It is intended to include the number of objects in specific scientific knowledge of a human in many of his or her links with the outside world, reproduction of a more or less full image of a person in the content of education , e.g., a person - a physical object and a physics system, conditioning the properties of the body by the conditions of the environment, the place and role of a human in the socio-cultural context of the epoch and in the "Nature -Science - Technology - Society -Human", etc. The subject of "Physical Culture" provides great possibilities for inclusion of anthropological knowledge and technologies in the curriculum.

7. The Sensitive-reflective component implies that the knowledge obtained in the educational process of physical training should contribute to the formation of the axiological and aesthetic regulators of informative and professional activities.

8. The Information-analytical component takes into account the peculiarities of the formation and creative development of the individual in terms of the formation of a new paradigm of informatization of the human society. The process of development of students' intellectual component of physical culture provides the formation of basic knowledge and skills of the integrated use of various channels of obtaining and semantic processing of information in a rapidly changing information environment. This component focuses on the development of mechanisms for the rapid preparation, choice, selection of the meaning structure and analysis of information (in proceedings of print, electronic, video and audio materials) of the peculiarities of the human body, about the possibilities and methods of personal improvement and optimization of the physical condition. It provides the formation of the person who is mastering the multi-dimensional information activity and is able to independently navigate and operate successfully in a dynamic information environment [3].

9. The Cognitive-communicative component provides the development of the basic foundations of decoding information of different kinds of verbal and nonverbal communications and interactions in the socio-cultural and professional aspects. It is relevant in respect of the increasing scope of information and communication channels, which the students adjoin to. In respect to the subject of "Physical culture" it means forming the person on the verbal-semantic, pragmatic and cognitive, motivational levels to be capable of overcoming the barriers of various kinds of background (cultural, verbal and pragmatic) to achieve their strategic and tactical goals.

10. The Creative-developing personal-variable component is expressed in gradual replacement of informative methods of teaching by personal-active and research, implying the use of person-centered and variant pedagogics of teaching, personally

oriented elective courses, individualized according to the type of physical and psychological characteristics of the student. This component is based on the principles of polivariance and diversity of sports education, it provides the conditions for a more complete manifestation of abilities of students in their chosen forms of physical and sports activities organized according to their value orientations and athletic interests. Wide and multi-level use of modeling the technologies of personalized control actions according to the age, psycho-physiological, intellectual, morphological and functional features of the student creates conditions for a full demonstration and development of personal competences of subjects of the educational process, their creative self-expression and self-realization and development of the appropriate level of intellectual ability in the organization of their own physical activity.

11. The Regional-ethnic component is intended for new non-traditional approaches to the aims and tasks of the organization of the educational process, taking into account national, cultural and regional characteristics. It is necessary to use in the process of teaching of the subject "Physical Culture" the fact that for centuries in the history of human culture a great experience has been accumulated in the use of various forms of organized physical activity by which the representatives of different nations have not only worked out certain physical but also psychological characteristics. The component under review involves taking into account the evolution of psychophysiological characteristics of students within the cultures of which they are the representatives, as humanistic ideas in any national culture have both similarities and profound differences associated with the originality of the philosophical and religious thought, the spiritual mentality of the people and the Doctrine of the Faith, with a particular historical development. This component is based on the principles of ethnic and cultural identity and integration into the world community.

12. The Cultural-infusion component solves the problem of learning the "culture of communication", it is particularly relevant in view of the fact that the development of modern information technologies and the expansion of international relations inevitably lead to the interaction and interpenetration of previously marginalized cultures. Having mastered the system of background knowledge, i.e. the aggregation of cultural, geographical, historical information, views on national traditions, customs and realities of the country, sports and athletic achievements of its representatives, a future specialist is capable of understanding and interacting with speakers of different languages and carriers of different cultures.

13. The Applicative-valeologi-cal component is intended to master a system of practical skills, ensuring the preservation and promotion of health, mental well-being, development and improvement of mental and physical abilities and personal features, and self-determination in physical education. It encompasses the complex of those principles, techniques, methods of teaching which allots them features of health preservation in addition to the traditional technology of training and education. Since the purpose of discipline "Physical Culture" is the formation of the physical culture of the individual and the ability to use a variety of tools aimed at Physical Culture, Sports and Tourism in order to preserve and promote health, psychophysical training and self-training for future careers, in this aspect the teaching of physical culture is more fully investigated in literature, so we will not dwell on it.

14. The Contemporal-Presenta-tional component, being also a part of the general humanitarian basis of education, provides correlation of curriculum content with the current level of scientific knowledge and the cultural, political, social, economic realities of the society at the national, regional and planetary levels. It allows for the renewal, development and improvement of the content aspects of the values of physical training, the need for constant updating of knowledge in connection with the development of the society and culture.

15. The Psychological-adaptive component provides the mastery of methods of psychological self-regulation, the active management of their own psychological state and reactions in the process of physical training.

As an illustration, we present a small example of one of the important components which is based on the proposed concept model of humanitarian-developing educational environment - ethical-axiological component, providing for the identification and use of a comprehensive ethical-humanistic potential of physical culture. The International Charter of Physical Education and Sport emphasizes that "physical education and sport should make a more effective contribution to the inculcation of fundamental human values underlying the full development of peoples, ... should seek to promote closer communion between peoples and between individuals. Physical education and sport should strengthen its educational impact in order to assert the basic human values that are the basis for the full development of nations" [6]. Problematic value-relevant situations are an important form of pedagogical situations, used in the formation of values relating to humanitarian cognition. They suggest a piece of content of socio-cultural reality, presented in the form of a controversy that was significant enough for a human of the past as well as for the contemporary. The method of parenting situations is also called the method of organizing the activities and behaviour of students in special circumstances. For the successful application of parenting situations they should not be far-fetched and fragmented, and they should reflect life with all its contradictions and complexities. First of all, these are the situations in which a student can decide any issue of moral choice, method of organizing activities, the choice of social roles, etc. In the method of solving moral dilemmas (developed by L. Kohlberg [7]) the problem situation is not only analyzed, but also the spiritual and axiological relations of a student are identified and formed. A collective analysis of the dilemmas leads to the perception of a mate and a teacher as the carriers of other meanings, values; it allows looking at the situation from different points of view, seeing its volume and

multidimensional character. As noted by Paul Kurtz [8], the moral dilemma in which our principles and values are tested, is the main problem of ethics. As an example, let's consider the dilemma Zidane - Ma-terazzi.

The Final of World Cup-2006 will be remembered for a long time, but not only for its unexpected outcome, although the definition of the champion with a penalty shoot-out is a rare event. Perhaps for the first time the events of the match do not directly concern purely sports, but the very humane, that is, universal, aspects of life. Approximately 10 minutes before the end of extra time of the final match of the World Cup-2006 between the teams of France and Italy, the legendary French footballer Zinedine Zidane, the captain and the best player of the World Cup-2006, hit his head on the chest of Italian defender and team captain Marco Materazzi. Materazzi fell like a stone, and the judge sent Zidane off the field. This match was the last for Zidane in the national team in his 20-year football career. Italy went on to win the World Cup in a penalty shoot-out in the absence of the red-carded Zidane. Later Zidane explained that Materazzi insulted his mother and sister rudely, and he repeated these words several times. Therefore, he could not restrain himself and hit the offender. In this case, the legendary French footballer, who after the World Cup-2006 ended his career, said that he apologized to the millions of children who watched the final match France - Italy on-line: "Sure, it's something one should not do, and I want to say it loud and clear, I apologize to the millions of children who saw this act, to the educators who tell children what is right and wrong. But I cannot regret my action. That would mean that he was right and he cannot be right, absolutely not. What I deplore is that they always punish the reaction. But if there were no provocation, there would be no reaction. Do you think that ten minutes from the end of my career I would do such a thing for the fun of it? Sure, my action is unforgivable, but the really guilty one should also be punished. And the really guilty one is the one who provokes" [9]. Materazzi declined to comment on the case, saying that winning the World Cup is worth a lot.

Summary

In conclusion we should note that the ethical position ensures the integrity of subject-formation of a person and appears as both a moral position (personal, corresponding to an external standard of conduct), ethical (individual, defined by a specific system of meanings) and spiritual (subjective, affirming the values of activities). The concept developed by us allows specifying the problem of actualization of humanitarian potential of the discipline "Physical Culture" in terms of aims and means of the educational system. In this case, physical education can be well represented in the humanitarian space of the university, covering cultural, philosophical, psychological, social, and pedagogical aspects of the educational process.

Conclusions

We believe that the insertion of the discipline "Physical Culture" in the structure of the general humanitarian basis of education will help to overcome the shortage of humane culture in the socio-cultural environment of the university. On the basis of the conceptual-theoretical model of local humanitarian-developing educational environment adapted to the educational discipline "Physical Culture" it is advisable to establish humanitarian-oriented teaching tools and computer programs, the purpose of which is to form a coherent structure of value and meaning systems that determine mentality of a future specialist, through the prism of which there comes the awareness of a rapidly changing world and a human's place in it, the development of value-semantic relation to each issue (global or local, mass or individual), the vision of its inner human meaning and understanding of its positive (or destructive) effects; the development of intellectual and personal qualities such as openness to the new, tolerance, understanding many facets of the world, its ambiguity.

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